

1 **Plasma metabolomic signatures for copy number variants and**

2 **COVID-19 risk loci in Northern Finland Populations**

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22 **Abstract**

23 Here, we present genome-wide metabolomic signatures for copy-number variants (CNV) and single
24 nucleotide polymorphisms (SNP) in two Finnish cohorts - The Northern Finland Birth Cohort 1966 (NFBC
25 1966) and NFBC 1986. This work builds upon our earlier study of characterising common CNVs in the
26 TSPAN8 gene. Here, we have carried out an analysis of CNVs in over 9,300 individuals and characterised
27 their dosage effect (CNV-metabolomic QTL) on 228 plasma lipoproteins and metabolites. We have
28 reported reference (normal physiology) metabolomic signatures for up-to ~2.6 million COVID-19 GWAS
29 results from the GRASP database, including for outcomes related to COVID-19 death, severity, and
30 hospitalisation. Furthermore, by analysing two exemplar genes for COVID-19 severity namely LZTFL1

31 and OAS1, both reported to have Neanderthal ancestry, we have reported here two additional candidate
32 genes for COVID-19 severity biology, namely 1) NFIX, a gene related to viral (adenovirus) replication and
33 hematopoietic stem cells and 2) ACSL1, a known candidate gene for sepsis and bacterial inflammation.
34 Based on our results and current literature we hypothesise that 1) charge imbalance across the cellular
35 membrane between cations (Fe^{2+} , Mg^{2+} etc) and anions (e.g., ROS, hydroxide ion from cellular Fenton
36 reactions, superoxide etc), 2) iron trafficking within and between different cell types e.g., macrophages and
37 3) systemic oxidative stress response (e.g., lipid peroxidation mediated inflammation), together could be of
38 relevance in severe COVID-19 cases. To conclude, our unique atlas of univariate and multivariate
39 metabolomic signatures for CNVs (~7.2 million signatures) and SNPs (~0.7 million signatures) with deep
40 annotations of various multi omics data sets provide an important reference knowledge base for human
41 metabolism and diseases.

42

43 **Introduction**

44 Copy-number variation (CNV) is an important class of mutation which affects roughly 9-10% of the human
45 genome sequence. Several landmark studies have profiled CNVs in large disease and multi ancestry
46 populations and some recent studies have characterised CNVs in longitudinal cohorts^{1,2}. Current literature
47 suggests that the functional effects of CNVs remain relevant in neuropsychiatric disorders³ and cancer⁴⁻⁶
48 but their full relevance in common heritable diseases or their role in normal human physiology and
49 phenotypes still remains unclear and perhaps underdetermined⁷. In our previous study⁸, we successfully
50 characterised several common CNVs in the TSPAN8 gene and showed that it has a pleiotropic effect on a
51 large number of metabolites. Here, we have extended our previous analysis and report genome wide
52 autosomal results for CNV analysis in over 9,300 Northern Finland individuals and the quantitative effect
53 of these CNVs on 228 ¹H NMR characterised lipid and fatty acid phenotypes. Our multimodal association
54 analysis of genomic variations including CNVs, single nucleotide variation (SNP), Log R Ratio (LRR)
55 using both univariate and multivariate models resulted in a diverse class of metabolomic signatures, which
56 were further enriched by extensive multi omics annotations. Importantly, as an exemplar analysis, we were

57 able to successfully characterise metabolomic signatures of known COVID-19 gwas loci in our cohorts and
58 discover novel biology related to iron trafficking (cation-anion exchange or charge imbalance) and
59 macrophages. We note that these results can explain a substantial number of observations from current
60 literature on COVID-19 disease biology for OAS1 and LZTFL1. In summary, our results provide a
61 landscape of CNVs observed in a large bottlenecked Finnish longitudinal cohort and further substantiates
62 its dosage effect on 228 metabolite measurements. This rich resource of metabolic signatures with an
63 extensive multi omic annotation database is likely to be an important knowledge base for human genetic
64 variation and its effect on diseases.

65

66 **Results**

67 **CNV landscape**

68 In NFBC 1986, genotyped on Illumina Cardio metabochip, we detected 863,753 distinct CNV breakpoints,
69 with most overlapping with each other. Out of these, 246 were homozygous deletions (CNV type 0), 84,524
70 heterozygous deletions (CNV type 1), 550,829 heterozygous duplications (type 3) and 228,154
71 homozygous duplications (type 4) (**Figure 1a**). In NFBC 1966, we detected 510,622 distinct CNV
72 breakpoints with 1751, 296040, 195322 and 17509 counts for CNV types 0,1, 3, and 4 respectively (**Figure**
73 **1b**). Based on expected CNV genotypes, the most common genic CNV was found to be in the gene
74 OLFML2B (1:161976988, type 3 and 4, MAF=0.5) for NFBC 1986 and in LRRK2 (12:40601708, type 1,
75 3 and 4, MAF=0.447) for NFBC 1966. LRRK2 also harboured the most common meta analysis CNV for
76 NFBC 1986 and NFBC 1966 (12:40601708, type 1, 3 and 4, MAF=0.447). As per CNV validation, 21,144
77 and 18,124 NFBC CNVs loci overlapped with WTCCC CNV study and 1KG CNV results respectively
78 (**Figure 1c, 1d**). Further details of CNV breakpoints, their annotations and lipid signatures are available in
79 an accompanying multi omics signature database **supplementary table 1**. Of note, all reported CNVs here
80 have at least one probe with association p value ~ 0.05 with one or more of the metabolomic phenotypes.

81

82 **Metabolomic signatures**

83 Based on CNV genotypes and LRR measurements (with 50 LRR pcs as covariates), we generated univariate
84 and multivariate metabolomic signatures from 228 ¹H NMR metabolites (**Supplementary table 2**) for
85 genotyping probes in NFBC 1986 (n=196,475) and for probes in NFBC 1966 (n=382,960) and in addition
86 for common probes (n=10,764) between the two cohorts. The univariate association results consisted of a)
87 ~1.93 million association results in NFBC 1986 (**Figure 2a**), b) ~3.43 million association results in NFBC
88 1966 (**Figure 2b**) c) 328,985 meta analysis (**Figure 2c**) and d) 968,867 pooled association results
89 (**Supplementary table 3**). The most significant locus in the meta analysis was in the FADS2 gene
90 (11:61605215) with p value 1.06e-49 (n=8,630, MAF=0.07) for the phenotype FAW3_FA (**Figure 1**). In
91 the pooled analysis, a locus in the LRRK2 gene (12:40601708) was most significant with p value <
92 2.225074e-308 for the phenotype Crea. In the multivariate multiphen approach for CNV genotypes (all
93 phenotypes used together in a single model) the most significant locus was in the gene CLCN6
94 (1:11900825) with p value ~ 2.22e-308 and the most significant multivariate signature (variable selection)
95 was found to be located in a intergenic region with p value ~ 2.22e-308, MAF=0.164 and a signature
96 consisting of 31 metabolites (**Supplementary table 3**). We observed similar trends in CNV pleiotropy
97 across NFBC 1986 and NFBC 1966 (**Figure 3**). Next, we repeated this analysis using only LRR
98 measurements. In total we generated ~7.2 million CNV genotype signatures and ~6.5 million LRR
99 signatures across all cohorts and approaches. In addition, we have also reported nominal SNP signatures
100 for NFBC 1986 and NFBC 1966 ~ 0.6 million association results. We applied a global filter of p value ~
101 0.05 to all signatures.

102

103 **Metabolomic signatures for COVID-19 GWAS loci**

104 We downloaded UK Biobank GWAS results for COVID-19 from the GRASP database which were divided
105 into categories related to COVID-19 a) susceptibility b) death c) hospitalisation and d) severity
106 (**Supplementary table 4**). In total we obtained 65 GWAS cohorts across all ancestry groups which were
107 further stratified by gender. Next, leveraging genomic location or in a variant (CNV or SNP) agnostic way,

108 we were able to match ~2.6 million COVID-19 GWAS results to NFBC 1986 and NFBC 1966 metabolomic
109 signatures at a p value threshold of ~0.05. Across all 65 groups, the top two most significant loci were: rank
110 1) ABO (9:136145425, rs9411378, MAF=0.22, p value= 8.6e-11) and rank 2) LZTFL1 (3:45864732,
111 rs10490770, MAF=0.07, p value = 5.03e-10). The most significant locus (rank=1) associated with death in
112 the European population was in the gene APOE (19:45410002, rs769449, MAF=0.12, P value=3.16e-7)
113 (**Figure 4**). Of note, allele frequency of rs769449 is variable across different populations with highest
114 frequency in the Finnish population with MAF=0.16, Non-Finnish European population with MAF=0.11,
115 East Asian MAF=0.08 and African/African-American MAF=0.01. We have reported the druggability
116 options for rs769449 in our multi omics database. Further, as an exemplar case study, we analysed in detail
117 two well known genes for COVID-19 severity namely a) LZTFL1 and b) OAS1 - both reported to have
118 Neanderthal origins^{9,10}. We carried out comprehensive genome wide signature analysis for both these genes
119 using CNV genotypes and LRR across all datasets and methods. We found a general trend, in particular for
120 meta analysis and pooled analysis of NFBC 1986 and NFBC 1966, where both LZTFL1 and OAS1
121 consistently had a high signature overlap with NFIX and ACSL1 (**Supplementary table 5**). In this
122 signature analysis we also discovered a new gene of interest OASL, an important paralog of OAS1, which
123 is known to be involved in interferon gamma signalling.

124 **Summary of multi-omics annotations**

125 The beacon section of the multi-omics signature database lists all genomic probes with their location (hg19),
126 variant effect (intron, exon, intergenic etc) and HGNC gene family (**Supplementary table 1**). All probes
127 are annotated with flags (yes=1,no=0) for metabolomic signatures, LRR signatures and presence of CNV
128 genotypes in NFBC 1986 or NFBC 1966. CNVs are validated by the WTCCC CNV study results (21,144
129 loci validated) and thousand genomes CNV results (18,124 loci validated). Metabolomic signatures are
130 validated with annotations from the global lipids consortium database (1,867 loci validated). In addition,
131 the beacon section also has numerous flags in order to look up other multi omics data present in the database
132 (e.g. GWAS catalogue, OMIM, druggability etc). Some highlights of other data tables in the database

133 include drugbank information for up to 24,380 metabolomic signatures, ~2 million matching eQTL signals
134 from the GTex database, reference metabolomic signature for ~14,000 OMIM/Orphanet mendelian disease
135 genes, 37,862 loci overlapping with a known cancer driver mutation (in a 4 base pair window) and
136 importantly, a fully annotated database table for up to ~2.6 million GWAS results for UK Biobank COVID-
137 19 analysis, stratified by ancestry and gender.

138

139 **Discussion**

140 CNVs remain relevant in current literature and are often reported in human genetic studies related to rare
141 diseases, cancer and neuropsychiatric disorders. Due to the high deleterious effect of CNVs on human
142 phenotypes it is important to explore their effect on intermediate phenotypes such as lipids, fatty acids and
143 various classes of metabolites. Recently several SNP based metabolomic-QTL studies were successful in
144 demonstrating that ¹H NMR based metabolomic measurements from a single drop of blood can prove to be
145 a powerful tool for simultaneously predicting morbidity and many common diseases^{11,12}. However, at
146 present there are relatively few studies with large sample sizes analysing the dosage effect of CNVs on the
147 normal human metabolome. Our study here addresses this important knowledge gap in current literature
148 and further leverages these results to uncover an important piece of biology related to COVID-19 severity
149 (further discussed below). Some comparable studies to ours are the recently published metabolome GWAS
150 analysis of the UK and Japan Biobanks. Here, we highlight some distinguishing features of our study. First,
151 our discovery and replication cohorts are from a bottlenecked and linguistically isolated population from
152 Northern Finland, hence, less likely to be confounded by population structure or phenotypic heterogeneity.
153 Second, unlike the UK Biobank study where there was a minimum of four hour gap between last meal and
154 blood collection, in the NFBC study all participants were subject to overnight fasting. A CNV-metabolomic
155 QTL analysis of the UK Biobank has not been reported so far but may be expected in future data releases.
156 Such datasets will provide an important benchmark for comparing and contrasting reference metabolism in
157 humans. In addition, it will further aid in the interpretation and fine mapping of genomic loci with a-priori
158 disease hypothesis from the large compendium of current GWAS studies. In the long term such biomarker

159 related information could be very useful for population level healthcare practices related to prognosis of
160 common diseases, ageing, physiology (BMI, height) and lifestyle based outcomes such as educational
161 attainment, medication use, diet etc. Our comprehensive set of metabolomic signatures covers several
162 different modalities of genomic variation including CNVs, Log R Ratio and SNPs. Each class of genomic
163 variation is further analysed through univariate and multivariable association models resulting in 24
164 MGWAS and over 300 million effect sizes and p values (~ 0.05). The accompanying multi omics annotation
165 database further provides genomic and disease specific context for all reported metabolomic signatures and
166 contains a beacon table which provides comprehensive cross referencing of all results. The database could
167 potentially be updated and integrated with other datasets in future thus providing new insights and
168 understanding with time. As an exemplar case study of the application of our metabolomic signatures, here,
169 we discuss in detail the cellular biology of two well known genes for COVID-19 severity namely LZTFL1
170 and OAS1. Both these genes have Neanderthal origins and were reported to be strongly associated with
171 severe COVID-19 by several independent studies^{9,10}. In our genome wide signature comparison analysis,
172 we found LZTFL1 to be closely related to NFIX and OAS1 to be linked to both NFIX and ACSL1. Next,
173 based on current literature, we elucidate how these genes relate to the biology of severe COVID-19.

174
175 First, we make important observations regarding the role of oxylipins in resident macrophages, ACSL1 and
176 other members of the ACSL gene family in bacterial inflammation cases of neonatal sepsis^{13,14}. Current
177 literature suggests that there are several different isoforms of the ACSL gene family with varied expression
178 and function in different tissues¹⁵⁻¹⁷. For instance, ACSL1 and ACSL4 isoforms are active in the liver but
179 ACSL3 and ACSL6 isoforms are predominantly active in the brain. We highlight five members of this gene
180 family (ACSL1,3-6) have a common function of transporting oxylipins into the mitochondria and further
181 note that ACSL1 and ACSL4 but not ACSL6 are inhibited by Triacsin C, an inhibitor of long fatty acyl
182 CoA synthetase. Of note, ACSL1 and ACSL4 can induce ferroptosis (iron dependent cell death) through
183 independent mechanisms¹⁸⁻²¹. A recent study also explains the role of ACSL3 and ACSL4 in iron related
184 oxidative cell injury and cell death due to lipid peroxidation of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs)²². In

185 immunometabolism, oxylipins, along with other classes of oxysterols such as the CH25H are known to
186 activate immune cells such as macrophages²³ and B cells. Such cascades of immune activation, which is
187 essentially a countermeasure to stop lipid peroxidation²⁴ (or free radical propagation) across the body and
188 prevent oxidative tissue damage, however in consequence can lead to inflammation or formation of plaques,
189 as often seen in multiple tissues such as blood vessels, arteries and brain cells²⁵. We postulate that such
190 inflammation mediated tissue degeneration, if indeed operative in COVID-19, could be an explanation for
191 symptoms related to hyperinflammation²⁶ and multi organ failures seen in severe cases²⁷.

192
193 Next, we highlight results from two landmark studies related to COVID-19 namely the GWAS analysis of
194 severe COVID-19²⁸ and the COVID-19 host genetics initiative^{29,30}. In figure 2 of the first study²⁸, we note
195 that OAS1 and ACSL6 had significant change in protein concentration in the generalised summary-level
196 data Mendelian randomization (GSMR) results for RNA expression analysis. This GSMR result possibly
197 suggests that there is a switch of cellular function from OAS1-ACSL1 pathways in healthy individuals, as
198 characterised by our metabolomic signatures in NFBC cohorts to OAS1-ACSL6 related severity pathways
199 in COVID-19. Further, based on results from this study and the COVID-19 host genetics initiative and its
200 update, we further highlight several other genes of interest for our COVID-19 severity hypothesis, namely
201 BCL11A, SLC22A31, SLC6A20, SLC2A5 and HBBP1. Here, we illuminate our hypothesis further in light
202 of these genes. First we note that both NFIX³¹ and BCL11A³² (a distal regulator of globin gene HBG1),
203 which was found to be significant both in the GSMR analysis and also in the COVID-19 host genetics
204 update, are regulators of the foetal haemoglobin (HbF). HBG1 and HBG2 which constitute the gamma
205 chains of HbF are normally expressed in foetal liver, spleen and bone marrow. HbF is slowly converted
206 into adult haemoglobin (HbA) during the initial months of a baby's development³². Based on these
207 observations we postulate that in contrast to adults, BCL11A through its regulation of HbF could possibly
208 have a protective effect in neonates and babies, who were relatively less affected by severe COVID-19. Of
209 note, normal serum iron levels in the blood is maximum in newborns (100-250 µg/dL) followed by adult
210 male (65-176 micro µg/dL/dL), adult females (50-170 µg/dL/dL) and children (50-120 micro µg/dL/dL)

211 (source url https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Serum_iron). Further, iron, which is an integral part of HbF, is
212 also a common element in the severe COVID-19 related gene CYP4B1²⁹ and LCN2³³. Continuing on the
213 theme of haematology, we highlight two other genes from our severity list namely 1) HBBP1 is a gene
214 involved in erythropoiesis³⁴ and 2) NFIX, a gene involved in life long sustenance of vertebrate blood³⁵.
215 NFIX (also known as CCAAT-binding transcription factor) has a dual role of acting as a RNA polymerase
216 II promoter for vertebrate globin genes³⁶ and also acts as an initiation factor for adenovirus DNA replication.
217 The NFIX CCAAT box transcription factor is also involved in oxidative stress response³⁷ during muscle
218 regeneration by macrophages. It also interacts with a non heme iron-binding protein Pirin (PIR) which in
219 turn is regulated by the antioxidant response gene NRF2^{38,39}. Other genes from our severity list include
220 SLC22A31, a gene responsible for organic anion transport across the cell membrane and SLC6A20, a gene
221 involved in Na(+)- and Cl(-)-dependent uptake of amino acids such as L-proline. SLC22A31 is a member
222 of the conserved OAT family of solute carriers^{40,41} which also has a closely related member gene
223 SLC22A17 (not reported to be associated with COVID-19 severity so far). SLC22A17⁴² is known for
224 regulating LCN2, an iron trafficking gene. LCN2 was recently shown to be important in
225 neuroinflammation⁴³ and also separately reported to be of significance by the COvid-19 Multi-omics Blood
226 ATlas (COMBAT) study³³. In the COMBAT study LCN2 was one of the main genes separating COVID-
227 19 severity groups of patients from sepsis. Further, a recent study⁴⁴ demonstrated that iron oxide
228 nanoparticles (IONPs) iron oxyhydroxide (IOHNPs) impairs SARS-CoV-2 virus in vitro and further
229 induces expression of LCN2 (seven-fold), SLC11A2 (encoding divalent metal transporter 1 (DMT1) also
230 known as Natural resistance-associated macrophage protein 2 (NRAMP 2)) (three-fold) and SLC40A1
231 (FPN1) (38-fold). IONPs have been shown to induce ROS and oxidative stress in different cell types
232 including macrophages^{45,46}.

233 Additionally, from the COVID-19 update study we highlight ATP5PO, a gene which is involved in proton
234 conductance in the mitochondrial matrix and ATP11A which is involved in influx of Ca²⁺ into the cells. In
235 normal human physiology, due to the toxic nature of iron and ROS, these entities are tightly regulated
236 within the cell and in the body. The daily dietary requirement for iron is only one milligram whereas the

237 rest of the requirement of two to three milligrams of iron is recycled inside the body from older cells, mainly
238 through dying red blood cells (RBCs). Macrophages are known to be one of the main cell types responsible
239 for iron recycling from RBCs and they can provide up to 75% of the total requirement⁴⁷. Erythropoiesis or
240 RBCs generation is a highly dynamic process and they are produced within the bone marrow at rates
241 exceeding 2 million new cells per second. To this end, we highlight that red-blood-cell count was found to
242 be the most significant protective trait against COVID-19 severity as depicted in figure 3 of the mendelian
243 randomisation analysis of COVID-19 host genetics study³⁰. Compared to most cells, RBCs have a short life
244 span of around 120 days. RBCs undergo de-nucleation during their initial development and inherently lack
245 mitochondria due to which they are not able to metabolise fatty acids, hence solely rely on glycolysis for
246 energy (ATP) production. This observation perhaps explains the importance of SLC6A5, a gene responsible
247 for the glycolysis and fructose transport from our severity list⁴⁸. The hypothesis that RBC lifespan gets
248 shortened or disrupted in conditions such as sepsis or severe COVID-19 perhaps warrants further
249 investigation. In humans, macrophages first develop during embryogenesis and subsequent to the yolk sac
250 phase of embryo development, these cells get distributed to major organs where they differentiate and
251 develop further as resident macrophages^{49,50}. During their lifetime, the resident macrophages maintain
252 tissue homeostasis and recycle iron and other metabolites from the tissue microenvironment⁵¹. Compared
253 to the blood monocyte derived non-resident macrophages, the resident macrophages self-renew and are
254 relatively long lived. These observations are of added importance for COVID-19 since results published in
255 a immunological study between adults and children demonstrates that the interaction of resident and non-
256 resident macrophages plays a key role in protecting young children against COVID-19^{26,52,53}.

257

258 Oxygen is the third most abundant element on the earth's crust followed by other metals including iron (the
259 most abundant transition earth metal) magnesium, cobalt, nickel etc. It has been reported that 10 to 15% of
260 human genes in the cell are switched on and off by oxygen availability, which in turn affects important
261 cellular functions like the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle, DNA replication, cell division or cell cycle
262 arrest⁵⁴. Of note, in COVID-19 severe cases as well as in sepsis, multiple studies have shown that oxygen

263 supply through ventilation is of critical importance for palliative care. We have already discussed the
264 importance of iron for COVID-19 severity, here, in addition, we highlight the putative role of Magnesium
265 in COVID-19. Magnesium like iron is a divalent cation and is part of more than 300 enzymes in the human
266 body and forms an important part of protein translation machinery⁵⁵ and protects the mitochondria from
267 oxidative stress⁵⁶. Magnesium is also an integral part of biochemistry of GTPase, guanine nucleotide
268 exchange factors (GEF) and GTPase-activating proteins (GAP)⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹. In this regard, we note several genes
269 of interest from these classes of enzymes and molecules from the COVID-19 host genetics published
270 results. Some examples include ARHGAP27, ARHGEF38, ARL17A and RAB2A (**Table 1,**
271 **supplementary table 6**).

272 The fundamental role played by elements such as iron, oxygen, cations and anions in human cell biology
273 or physiology⁶⁰ could potentially run very deep, but rarely measured or characterised in current human
274 sequencing studies³⁸. The role of such elements in disease pathogenesis perhaps remains under explored at
275 present⁶¹. Hence, it is possible that current modalities of sequencing DNA and RNA on its own may be
276 inadequate to fully understand the full spectrum of COVID-19 manifestations seen in humans. The link
277 between OAS1 and LTZFL1 through metabolomic signatures perhaps reflects cellular dynamics related to
278 charge, flux and metabolite concentration (e.g., ROS). Many of these events occur in small time changes
279 which are usually not considered in current investigations. For instance, iron trafficking can change
280 intracellular pH for a time duration of only a few minutes. Therefore such dynamics⁶² are unlikely to be
281 reflected through gene expression or genomic sequencing alone and might require new multi modal data
282 integration approaches in future⁶³. To conclude, based on our results and observations, here, we hypothesise
283 that iron trafficking, macrophage biology and ROS might have an important role to play in the pathogenesis
284 of severe COVID-19 (**Table 1, supplementary table 6**).

285

286 **Methods**

287 The Northern Finland Birth Cohort is a longitudinal cohort from Northern Finland consisting of children
288 (n=12,068) born in the provinces of Oulu and Lapland, Finland. All subjects in this cohort were recruited
289 between 1st January 1966 and 31st December 1966. The NFBC 1986 cohort study (n=9,432) is a subsequent
290 study to NFBC 1966, where subjects were recruited from the same area as NFBC 1966 but between the
291 period 1st July 1985 and 30th June 1986. Both studies have been approved by the ethics committee of
292 University of Oulu and the Northern Ostrobothnia Hospital. Briefly, all study subjects in NFBC 1986 and
293 NFBC 1966 were monitored from pregnancy to adolescence and blood samples were collected from study
294 participants at 31 years of age. Blood samples were drawn after overnight fasting and subsequently stored
295 in -80c. Next, high-throughput metabolomic measurements, including deep lipoprotein subclass
296 characterisation were made by NMR platform (Bruker AVANCE III spectrometer operating at 500 Mhz)
297 developed by Nightingale Healthcare Limited. Further details about metabolite particle sizes and ratios
298 have been reported in earlier studies¹¹ (**Supplementary table 2**). NFBC 1986 and NFBC 1966 were
299 genotyped on Illumina cardio MetaboChip and on Illumina 370 CNV duo chip at the Broad institute. Based
300 on genomic location (hg19) there was concordance in 10,764 of the genotyping probes between the two
301 genotyping platforms thus enabling pooled and meta-analysis for common probes across these two cohorts.

302

303 **Data normalisation and CNV calling**

304 All methods and software used in this study are based on an earlier reported pilot study⁸ where we
305 characterised common CNVs in the TSPAN8 gene. Briefly, prior to CNV calling, as data normalisation
306 procedure we corrected for genomic wave effects by applying a localised loess function in a 500 kb window
307 and corrected total intensity measurement - Log R Ratio (LRR) for GC content. Next, we used the cnvHap
308 algorithm⁶⁴ in its population aware mode with Illumina platform emission parameters to detect and
309 genotype CNVs in NFBC 1986 and NFBC 1966. cnvHap integrates Log R Ratio (LRR) and B Allele
310 Frequency (BAF) into a single CNV-SNP haplotype Hidden Markov Model for detecting and genotyping
311 CNVs. The main parameters used in this analysis were r_mean (average LRR-BAF cluster positions in

312 cnvHap model) values = [-5;-1;0;0.6;1;1.3;1.5] with 15 Expectation Maximisation (EM) iterations. The
313 HMM was run with four hidden states enabling it to capture both homozygous and heterozygous CNVs.

314

315 **Association analysis**

316 We next applied both univariate and multivariate models for associating expected CNV genotypes with 228
317 metabolomic phenotypes using the Muliphen R package⁶⁵. The multiphen multivariate model uses reverse
318 regression, where the outcome is expected CNV genotypes and predictors are metabolomic measurements.
319 As described in our earlier study⁸, a metabolomic signature is defined as a unique set of uncorrelated
320 metabolites obtained on application of backward variable selection to the joint model of the Multiphen
321 method. In all cases a robust set of covariates were used. This included 50 LRR principal components (PCs)
322 and gender. All univariate and multivariate metabolomic signatures for CNV genotypes were independently
323 validated (without CNV calling) by using LRR based association model with LRR 50 principal components
324 and gender as covariates. SNP association results are nominal and meant only for replication with gender
325 used as covariate (Genotype PCs not available). No SNP imputation was performed, hence results are
326 restricted to only the probes of the genotyping platform.

327

328 **COVID-19 GWAS annotations**

329 The GRASP database lists GWAS results for COVID-19 susceptibility from various studies including from
330 the UK Biobank (UKBB)⁶⁶. GWAS in the UKBB studies were performed with SAIGE software (v0.38)
331 with appropriate control for population stratification, relatedness and case-control imbalance, and further
332 adjusted for age, sex, and 10 genetic principal components. Variants were further filtered on imputation
333 quality ($r^2 > 0.3$), minor allele count (>2), and minor allele frequency (MAF >0.0001). Each release of
334 UKBB consisted of up to 65 GWAS further divided into the following groups 1) COVID-19 susceptibility
335 (cases, $n=18,481$) 2) COVID-19 hospitalisation ($n=3,260$) 3) Severe COVID-19 with respiratory failure
336 ($n=1,244$) and 4) COVID-19 related death ($n=1,104$). GWAS on data releases were further stratified by

337 sex, ancestry, and trans-ethnic groups namely 459,250 of European ancestry (EUR), 7,644 of African
338 ancestry (AFR), 9,417 of South Asian ancestry (SAS), and 11,009 of other ancestries (Other). Here, based
339 on genomic location (hg19) we juxtaposed results from these GWAS (n=612) to the metabolomic signatures
340 in NFBC 1966 and NFBC 1986 in a variant (CNV or SNP) agnostic way. A complete list of study groups
341 is provided in supplementary table 4.

342 **Multi-omic annotation database for metabolomic signatures**

343 In order to gain further biological insights we have developed a metabolomic signature database with
344 detailed multi-omic annotations for all our signatures and CNV maps in NFBC 1986 and NFBC 1966
345 (**Supplementary table 1**). The database consists of a beacon table, where all loci are cross referenced with
346 metabolomic signatures, CNVs and multiple other annotations collated from public databases, including
347 annotations from the global lipids consortium database.

348

349 **FIGURES**

350 **Figure 1. Length distribution of CNVs** a) NFBC 1986. b) NFBC 1966 c) NFBC CNVs validated by the
351 one thousand genomes study d) NFBC CNVs validated by the WTCCC CNV study.

352 **Figure 2. Manhattan plot for CNV associations with the top three metabolomic lipids.** a) NFBC 1986
353 b) NFBC 1966 c) Meta analysis of NFBC 1986 and NFBC 1966.

354 **Figure 3. CNV Pleiotropy.** Pleiotropy counts of CNV loci in NFBC cohorts. a) NFBC 1966 CNV
355 genotypes. b) NFBC 1986 CNV genotypes.

356 **Figure 4. Three dimensional structure of ApoE fusion protein.** Complement repeats (CR) in low-density
357 lipoprotein receptor (LDLR) protein have a high-affinity calcium-binding site allowing them to fold
358 properly. This figure shows ApoE amino acid residues 130-149 interacting with CR17 of LDLR-related
359 protein 1 bound to calcium ion (PDB id **2KNY**).

360 **Supplementary Figures**

361 **Supplementary figure 1. LD in OAS1.** Linkage disequilibrium plot stratified by ancestry for OAS1 gene
362 cluster in Topmed Phewas database for UK biobank (url <https://pheweb.org/UKB-TOPMed/>).

363 **Supplementary figure 2. LD in FADS1/FADS2.** Linkage disequilibrium plot stratified by ancestry for
364 FADS1/FADS2 gene cluster in Topmed Phewas database.

365 **Supplementary figure 3. Inflation factors.** Genomic inflation factors for the top three metabolites
366 associated with CNVs in a) NFBC 1986 b) NFBC 1966

367

368 TABLES

369 **Table 1. Summary of COVID-19 hallmarks and the genes associated with them**

370 **Supplementary table 1.** Descriptions of the tables in the multi omic MySQL database for metabolomic
371 signatures

372 **Supplementary table 2.** Annotations for the NFBC metabolomic lipid names and categories

373 **Supplementary table 3.** CNV genotype association results and inflation factors

374 **Supplementary table 4.** Annotations for UK biobank COVID-19 GWAS study names

375 **Supplementary table 5.** Genome wide signature comparison of OAS1, LZTFL1, ACSL1 and NFIX

376 **Supplementary table 6.** COVID-19 gene descriptions and hallmarks

377

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380

COVID-19 Hallmark	Genes
Hematological	ABO, BCL11A, FUT2, GATA2, ICAM4, LZTFL1, PLSCR1, SLC22A5, THBS3, TCF7L2
Divalent cations - Fe(2+)/Mg(2+)/Ca(2+)	ANXA11, CIB4, CYP4B1, FDX2, MBL1P, NUCB1, PIR, SLC39A8
GTPase/GEF/GAP family, Protein translation	ARHGAP27, ARHGEF38, ARL17A, CEP97, EIF5AL1, LZTFL1, PLEKHM1, RAB2A, RASIP1
Voltage-gated ion transport, Mitochondria, ROS, Neurological	ACSF3, ATP11A, ATP5PO, ATP6V1G2, CAT, FOXG1, HCN3, KCNC3, MRPS6, MTX1, NSF, RPL24, SLC22A31, SLC34A2, SLC6A20, TOMM7, TRIMM46, TTC10
Macrophage biology	CCR1, CCR2, CCR3, CCR5, CSF3, ICAM3, IRF1, IRF7, NR1H2

381
382 **Table 1. Summary of COVID-19 hallmarks and the genes associated with them.** Genes listed above
383 have been reported to have significant association with COVID-19 either from the GWAS of COVID-19
384 host genetics initiative study or the study involving GWAS of COVID-19 severity groups (including
385 GSMR analysis) (**Supplementary table 6**).

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387
388

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392 computational analysis on the High Performance Computing Cluster (HPC).

393

Author contributions

394
395 T.D., L.J.M.C., M.R.J., and M-.R.J. were involved in study design, performed analysis, and wrote the
396 manuscript. M-.R.J. provided advice and access to NFBC cohorts, M-.R.J, L.J.M.C and M.R.J. advised

397 and supervised the CNV, metabolomics and multi phenotype association aspects of this work. All authors
398 contributed to the interpretation of COVID-19 biology and the discussion section of the manuscript.
399

400 **Declaration of interests / Competing interests**

401 No external or financial interests to be declared.

402 **Data and Code availability**

403 **Correspondence**

404 Further information and requests for resources and reagents should be directed to and will be fulfilled by
405 the lead contact, Dr Tisham De (tisham.de08@imperial.ac.uk or de.tisham@gmail.com).
406

407 **Materials availability**

408 NFBC material can be requested from the consortium website <https://www oulu.fi/nfbc/materialrequest>.
409

410 **Data and code availability**

411

412 **Data**

413

414 NFBC data are available with appropriate access permissions. Further details are available here

415 <https://www oulu.fi/nfbc/materialrequest>
416

417 An integrated multi-omics MySQL database which gives a wider context to our metabolomics association
418 results is available for public download from Zenodo.

419 **doi:** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12737754>
420

421 **Code**

422

423 All codes used to process and analyse data are published, and the source code is currently available at.

424 MultiPhen: <https://github.com/lachlancoin/MultiPhen>

425 cnvHap: <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/people/l.coin>

426 cnvHitSeq: <https://sourceforge.net/projects/cnvhitseq>
427

428 **Additional information**

429 Any additional information required to reanalyze the data reported in this paper is available from the lead
430 contact upon request.
431

432 This study did not generate new reagents or software code.
433

434 **Supplementary information**

435 **Urls**

- 436 1. COVID 19 GWAS results from GRASP database: (Ref [https://www.cell.com/hgg-](https://www.cell.com/hgg-advances/fulltext/S2666-2477(22)00011-2)
437 [advances/fulltext/S2666-2477\(22\)00011-2\)](https://www.cell.com/hgg-advances/fulltext/S2666-2477(22)00011-2)
438 <https://grasp.nhlbi.nih.gov/Covid19GWASResults.aspx>
439 2. Gene cards: <https://www.genecards.org/>
440 3. NFBC cohort details: [https://www.oulu.fi/en/university/faculties-and-units/faculty-](https://www.oulu.fi/en/university/faculties-and-units/faculty-medicine/northern-finland-birth-cohorts-and-arctic-biobank/northern-finland-birth-cohorts)
441 [medicine/northern-finland-birth-cohorts-and-arctic-biobank/northern-finland-birth-cohorts](https://www.oulu.fi/en/university/faculties-and-units/faculty-medicine/northern-finland-birth-cohorts-and-arctic-biobank/northern-finland-birth-cohorts)
442 4. Nightingale metabolomics platform: <https://nightingalehealth.com/technology>
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a

NFBC 1986 CNVs

b

NFBC 1966 CNVs

c

NFBC CNVs validated by Thousand Genomes CNV study

d

NFBC CNVs validated by WTCCC CNV study

Figure 1. Length distribution of CNVs. a) NFBC 1986. b) NFBC 1966 c) NFBC CNVs validated by the one thousand genomes study d) NFBC CNVs validated by the WTCCC CNV study.

Figure 2. **Manhattan plot for CNV associations with the top three metabolomic lipids.** a) NFBC 1986 b) NFBC 1966 c) Meta analysis of NFBC 1986 and NFBC 1966.

a

b

Figure 3. CNV Pleiotropy. Pleiotropy counts of CNV loci in NFBC cohorts. a) NFBC 1966 CNV genotypes. b) NFBC 1986 CNV genotypes.

Chain A Prolow-density lipoprotein receptor-related protein 1, Apolipoprotein E - Homo sapiens

a

b

Figure 4. **Three dimensional structure of ApoE fusion protein.** Complement repeats (CR) in low-density lipoprotein receptor (LDLR) protein have a high-affinity calcium-binding site allowing them to fold properly. This figure shows ApoE amino acid residues 130-149 interacting with CR17 of LDLR-related protein 1 bound to calcium ion (PDB id **2KNY**).

Supplementary figures

Hits in GWAS Catalog

Hits in GWAS Catalog

Hits in GWAS Catalog

Hits in GWAS Catalog

Hits in GWAS Catalog

Supplementary figure 1. **LD in OAS1.** Linkage disequilibrium plot stratified by ancestry for OAS1 gene cluster in Topmed Phewas database for UK biobank (url <https://pheweb.org/UKB-TOPMed/>).

Hits in GWAS Catalog

Hits in GWAS Catalog

Hits in GWAS Catalog

Hits in GWAS Catalog

Supplementary figure 2. **LD in FADS1/FADS2.** Linkage disequilibrium plot stratified by ancestry for FADS1/FADS2 gene cluster in Topmed Phewas database.

a

b

Supplementary figure 3. **Inflation factors.** Genomic inflation factors for the top three metabolites associated with CNVs in a) NFBC 1986 b) NFBC 1966